

Propargylation of some 3-Substituted-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-benzothiazoles. Propargyl-Allenyl Transformation. Mannich Base from Propargyl Derivative

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In view of the anticipated physiological activity¹ of some propargyl derivatives, propargylation of 3-hydroxy- and 3-mercapto-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazoles was undertaken. Propargyl bromide was reacted with 1 which gave corresponding compounds. With 3-hydroxy-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazole² the product was found to be 2-propargyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazol-3-one (2), whereas with 3-mercapto-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazole³ (6) the reaction yielded 3-propargyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazole (7).

We now report a novel propargyl-allenyl transformation that had taken place during the propargylation of 5- and/or 7-substituted-3-hydroxy- or 3-mercapto-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazoles⁴. Compound 1 along with propargylbromide was taken in equimolar proportion and allowed to react in presence of alkali. The product was found to be 2-allenyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazol-3-one (3) instead of 2-propargyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazol-3-one (2). The spectral data was in agreement with structure 3. The formation of 2-allenyl-*s*-triazolobenzothiazole might have proceeded through 2-propargyl-intermediate which in alkaline condition could have transformed into 2-allenyl- as presented in Scheme 1. This confirms allenyl structure (3) rather than propargyl structure (2). Five such new compounds (3a-e) were synthesised (Table 1).

The formation of 2-propyl-5-methyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazol-3-one (5a) from 2-allenyl compound (3a) by the reduction with Raney-Ni is confirmed by spectral data. The authentication was done by preparing 2-allyl-5-methyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazol-3-one (4a) from allyl bromide and the corresponding compound (1a). The reduction product from 2-allyl compound (4a) was identical in all respects to that obtained from 2-allenyl compound (3a).

Similar propargylation was carried out with 3-mercapto-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazoles (6) in alkali. The ir spectra of the product showed the absence of peaks at 1080, 1220 cm⁻¹ (C=S) suggesting that propargylation occurred at 3S' and not at 2N. Ir and nmr spectral data are in agreement with 3-allenyl structure. New compounds synthesised are 8a-e (Scheme 1). The allenic proton 1H (HC=C=) appears to have been masked with methyl protons. Downfield shift of 2H (=C=CH₂) in 3c and 8d may be due to anisotropic effect of ring current of aromatic system. For monosubstituted alkyl derivatives the values are within the normal range. When Raney-Ni reduction of 8a was carried out for getting 3-propylthio-5-methyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazole (10a), a compound with side-chain free moiety 5-methyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazole (9a) was obtained. The allenyl part along with sulphur was removed during desulphurisation, sulphur of thiazole ring remaining intact.

The acetylenic hydrogen of 3-propargylmercapto-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*]benzothiazole was found to be active and could be easily replaced by aminomethyl group. Formaldehyde and pyrrolidine taken alongwith compound 7 afforded 3-pyrrolidinomethylpropargylthio[3,4-*b*]benzothiazole (11). The same was not possible with 2-propargyl compound (2). This is because of lesser electronegativity of sulphur as compared to nitrogen.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 B spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO) on a FT-80 A (80 MHz)

For (3) and (8)

- a; R = CH₃, R' = H
- b; R = H, R' = CH₃
- c; R = H, R' = CH₃
- d; R = H, R' = C₂H₅O
- e; R = H, R' = NO₂

For (2) R = R' = H

Scheme 1

spectrometer. Elemental analyses were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer AD 22 autobalance. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

2-Allenyl-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazol-3-one (3a) : To 3-hydroxy-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (1.02 g, 0.005 mol) in 2*N* NaOH (10 ml), propargyl bromide (0.8 g, 0.0078 mol) was added and the solution was stirred for 2 h. The resulting yellow coloured solid was crystallised from ethanol, (66%),

m.p. 225°; δ 2.3(3H, CH₃), 4.2 (2H, allenyl), 7.1–7.8 (3H, ArH). Using the above procedure 3b-e were prepared (yields 66–74%) : 3b, m.p. 150° (EtOH), c, >320° (EtOH), δ 2.1–2.5 (6H, 2×CH₃), 6.1 (2H, allenyl), 7.0–7.1 (2H, ArH); d, 295°(EtOH); e, 320° (pet. ether).

Reduction of 2-allenyl-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazol-3-one to 5a : A mixture of 3a (1.22 g, 0.005 mol) and freshly prepared Raney-Ni (3 g) was refluxed in ethanol (60 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and removal of the solvent afforded 2-propyl-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazol-3-one (5a), which was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) as white crystals (0.6 g, 49%), m.p. 80° (C₁₂H₁₃N₃OS found : C, 57.9; H, 5.12; N, 17.76%); lack of ir peak at 2000 cm⁻¹ meant for cumulated double bond; δ (CDCl₃) 1.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.0 (2H, br, CH₂ attached to 2N), 1.9 (3H, s, CH₃ attached to benzene) and 7.8 (3H, m, ArH).

2-Allyl-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazol-3-one(4a) : To 3-hydroxy-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (1a; 1.53 g, 0.0075 mol) in 1*N* NaOH (30 ml) was added slowly allyl bromide (0.9 g, 0.0075 mol) with stirring for 2 h. It was then acidified with dilute HCl when red coloured sticky mass was obtained. It was trituration with ethanol to give pale brown crystalline product (4a; 1.4 g, 77%), m.p. 165° (C₁₂H₁₁N₃OS found : C, 58.51; H, 5.01; N, 16.89%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 720, 1 640, 1 300 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.5 (2H of allyl) and 7–7.8 (3H, m, ArH).

Reduction of 2-allyl-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazol-3-one (4a to 5a) : A mixture of 4a (0.61 g, 0.0025 mol) and freshly prepared Raney-Ni (1 g) was refluxed in ethanol (40 ml) for 2.5 h. The hot reaction mixture was then filtered and the filtrate upon evaporation yielded 5a (0.3 g, 48%), which was identical in all respect to the product obtained from 2-allenyl-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazol-3-one and having no depression n.m.m.p.

3-Allenylthio-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (8a-e) : To 3-mercapto-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (6a; 1.1g, 0.005 mol) taken in 2*N* NaOH (20 ml), propargyl bromide (1.8 g; 0.015 mol) was added slowly following the procedure mentioned for the preparation of 3, and other compounds (8b-e) were similarly isolated (yields 62–86%) : 8a, m.p. 160° (C₆H₆),

δ 2.8 (3H, CH₃), 4.5 (2H, allenyl), 7.2 (3H, ArH); b, 145° (EtOH), 2.7 (3H, CH₃), 4.4 (2H, allenyl), 7.0–7.1 (3H, ArH); c, 165° (C₆H₆); d, 120° (EtOH), δ 1.6 (3H, OCH₂CH₃), 4.3 (2H, OCH₂CH₃), 6.2 (2H, allenyl), 7.0–7.5 (3H, ArH); e, 96° (MeOH).

Attempted reduction of 3-allenylthio-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole to 3-propylthio-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole : A mixture of 3-allenylthio-5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (8a; 1.29 g, 0.005 mol) and freshly prepared Raney-Ni (3 g) was refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) for 6 h. The product was isolated by following the procedure given for the reduction of 4a. The compound was crystallised from ethanol to yield 5-methyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (9; 0.74 g, 78.7%), m.p. 231°; m.m.p. with the compound⁵ prepared from 2-hydrazino-4-methylbenzothiazole with formic acid remained undepressed.

Replacement of acetylenic hydrogen of 3-propargylthio-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (7) by an aminomethyl group. Mannich reaction : To 3-propargylthio-s-triazolo[3,4-b]benzothiazole (1.22 g, 0.025 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), formaldehyde (0.5 ml) solution (0.5 ml; 38/40, w/v) was added with stirring, followed by addition of pyrrolidine (0.35 g, 0.005 mol). The contents were warmed on a water-bath at 60° for 5 min and then kept overnight at room temperature. The

solvent was removed by evaporation and the resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol to yield 3-pyrrolidinomethylpropargylthio-s-triazolobenzothiazole (11; 1.0 g, 61%), m.p. 123° (C₁₆H₁₆N₄S₂ found : C, 57.96; H, 4.18; N, 16.66%). The compound was identified.

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